

ON THE ANTHOCYANIN PIGMENT IN THE RIND OF SUGAR-CANE (*PURPLE MAURITIUS*).

BY C. J. DASA RAO, D. G. WALAWALKAR AND B. S. SRIKANTAN.

The colouring matter in the rind of *Purple mauritius* cane, which persists in the sugar, has been isolated and has been identified to be a diglucoside of the monomethyl ether of delphinidin, possibly ampelopsidin. It has an absorption band in the region 4400-4800Å.

Considerable doubt exists as regards the nature of the soluble colouring matter in the rind of the purple cane and which being not easily removed from the cane juice, gives rise to difficulties during the refining of the sugar prepared from the cane. Harloff (*International Sugar Journal*, 1914, 16, 116) and Muller (*ibid.*, p. 224) identified it to be an anthocyanin from its colour reaction. Brewster (*ibid.*, 1923, 25, 593) does not agree with this view. Sakuma and Memosa (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind. Japan*, 1935, 38, 161, 224, 293) working with the rind of the Formosan cane, called "*Ancha*" have obtained the anthocyanin.

No attempt has been made so far to isolate the pigment in a pure form and identify it with one or more of the well known anthocyanins. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to isolate the colouring matter in a pure state and to elucidate its nature.

A preliminary colour reaction of the water extract of the rind by the method of Wheldale (*Biochem. J.*, 1913, 7, 87) showed that the substance belongs to the Weinroth group (*cf. Weigert, Jahres-Bericht*, Wien, 1895). The pigment from the rind of the cane has been extracted with glacial acetic acid, precipitated and recrystallised as red microscopic crystals from methyl alcoholic hydrogen chloride. The analytical data show the substance to be a glucoside of the formula $C_{28}H_{34}O_{17}Cl_4H_2O$. This is shown to be a diglucoside by hydrolysis with 20% hydrochloric acid. The anthocyanidin chloride then should be $C_{16}H_{12}O_7$, HCl. However, the anthocyanidin sulphate ($C_{16}H_{12}O_7$, H_2SO_4 , H_2O) was prepared by the method of Willstätter and Bolton (*Annalen*, 1915, 408, 42).

The Zeisel estimation showed the presence of only one methoxy group and the colour reactions of the demethylated product, when compared with those of the pelargonidin, cyanidin and delphinidin, clearly show that the substance is a delphinidin derivative. This evidence is fairly conclusive in the absence of alkali fusion and further study due to the insufficient quantity of the substance. Hence the anthocyanidin sulphate is a monohydrate of monomethylether of delphinidin sulphate.

There are five possible structures for the monomethyl ethers of delphinidin. The way of distinguishing these ethers is by alkali fusion of the demethylated product. The substance was too small for such

a procedure. The colour reactions agree well with those of ampelopsidin described by Willstätter and Zollinger (*Annalen*, 1916, 412, 164, 213, 216), Willstätter and Bendic (*Annalen*, 1916, 412, 217). These authors ascribe the following structure to ampelopsidin purely from ferric chloride reaction. The OMe-group is attached to the middle hydroxyl of the phenol residue of the molecule.

Hence it can be said with a fair degree of certainty that the anthocyanidin in the rind of the sugar-cane *purple mauritius* is a diglycoside of monomethyl delphinidin, possibly ampelopsidin, crystallising with 4 molecules of water. Willstätter and Zollinger (*loc cit.*), however, describe a monoglucoside of ampelopsidin, while they do not deny the possibility of a diglycoside being hydrolysed to monoglucoside during the process of preparation. The authors believe, however, further work is necessary before these tentative conclusions can be affirmed. The anthocyanin from *purple mauritius* is referred to in this work as *Mauritinin*.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Water Extract : Colour Reactions.—Mature canes possessing a dark violet tinted rind were taken and the epidermal layer was scraped by means of a piece of glass. The aqueous extract of the scrapings were red in colour and turned deep red in hydrochloric acid, dark green with sodium hydroxide and yielded a blue-green precipitate with neutral lead acetate. 0.10 G. of the pigment was obtained as a red powder in its non-glucosidal form, starting from 25 lbs. of cane. The substance was sparingly soluble in water and in dilute acid a crimson-red colour was obtained. Caustic soda and lime water gave a green colour, but with excess of the latter the colour was destroyed. Lead acetate produced a green precipitate. Absolute alcohol dissolved it giving brown-red solution. The red colour in mineral acid was taken up by amyl alcohol layer when shaken up with amyl alcohol.

Isolation of Mauritinin Chloride.—650 lbs. of mature *purple mauritius* cane were scraped and the scrapings (about 8 lbs.) put into 5 kg. of glacial acetic acid and allowed to stand for 7 days. The extract had a deep red colour with a faint green fluorescence. To each 500 c.c. of the extract

50 c.c. of methyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid (8%) was added and the pigment was precipitated by the addition of 1 litre of ether.

The impure product was dissolved by boiling for a short time in 2% methyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid, filtered warm to remove insoluble impurities and the filtrate mixed with $\frac{1}{2}$ its volume of aqueous hydrochloric acid, when the glucoside is not hydrolysed even on long standing. On cooling the chloride separated as a violet-red precipitate which was filtered and the precipitate again dissolved in methyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid and reprecipitated by aqueous hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was filtered and washed free of chloride and dried on a porous plate.

It is brown-red in colour, soluble in alcohol giving a purple solution. On dilution it isomerises to the pseudo-base of yellow colour. An acid solution treated with sodium carbonate yields violet colouration. Ferric chloride in alcoholic solution gives a violet colour and lead acetate a light blue precipitate.

The dehydrated product has an approximate M.W. (Rast) of 702. The dehydrated anthocyanin chloride gives on complete hydrolysis 50.08% of glucose. [Found : C, 49.27 ; H, 5.76 ; Cl, 5.18. Monoglucoside of ampelopsidin ($C_{22}H_{23}O_{12}Cl$) requires M. W., 514; glucose, 35.02% ; C, 51.36 ; H, 4.47 ; Cl, 6.18 per cent. Diglucoside of ampelopsidin ($C_{38}H_{39}O_{17}Cl$) requires M.W., 676; glucose, 53.25% ; C, 49.70 ; H, 4.88, Cl, 5.18 per cent]. The percentage of water in the air-dried sample, found by vacuum drying, is found to be 9.15%. On calculation it is seen that 9.62% of water are contained in $C_{28}H_{29}O_{17}Cl, 4H_2O$. The percentage of hydrogen is noticeably in excess perhaps due to incomplete dehydration of the substance in the last stages.

Hydrolysis of Mauritinin chloride and the Determination of Glucose.—

A weighed quantity of chloride was hydrolysed by boiling with 10 c.c. of 20% hydrochloric acid (*cf.* Willstätter and Meig, *Annalen*, 1915, 508, 61) and the mixture at once cooled. The solution was neutralised with sodium hydroxide and the glucose estimated by the method of Scales (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1915, 23, 61). A number of determinations were made with duration of hydrolysis varying from 3 to 7 minutes. As seen from below complete hydrolysis is obtained in 5 minutes.

3 min.	hydrolysis gave	23.98%
4		42.50
5		50.00
7		50.08

Isolation of the Mauritinin Sulphate.—10 lbs. of the scrapings from 800 lbs. of mature purple mauritius were collected in a large glass jar containing 1 lb. of glacial acetic acid. The method of Willstätter and

Bolton (*loc. cit.*) was followed and the lead salt was hydrolysed by 7% sulphuric acid. A brown-red powder was obtained which was difficult to crystallise, yield 0.6508 g.

It does not melt even at 300°. It forms an orange solution in alcohol giving yellow colouration with sodium carbonate and red with acids. Ferric chloride gives a faint green colour turning to violet. Caustic soda produces a permanent blue colour. An alcoholic solution containing 0.009 g. in 500 c.c. of absolute alcohol with a cell of 10 mm. thickness showed a strong band in indigo-blue region 4400-4800Å with diffuse ends. The substance when heated with nitric acid at 320° in a sealed tube and treated with BaCl₂ showed the presence of sulphate radicle. Loss of moisture in the air-dried sample at 100° under vacuum is 5%, giving 1 mol. of water in C₁₆H₁₂O₇, H₂SO₄, H₂O. The approximate M. W. of the dehydrated substance by Rast's method is 434. The substance was found to be a monomethoxy derivative, the dehydrated substance giving 7.93 and 7.79% of methoxyl groups in two Zeisel determinations. Monomethyl ether of delphinidin sulphate (C₁₆H₁₂O₇, H₂SO₄) requires 7.38% and the dimethyl ether of delphinidin sulphate (C₁₇H₁₄O₇, H₂SO₄) requires 12.15%. The slightly higher values for OMe is usual in most of monomethyl ethers of the delphinidin group, perhaps due to traces of dimethyl ether as impurity (*cf.* Perkin and Everest, "The Natural Organic Colouring matters" 1918, p. 315).

The Demethylated Mauritinidin Chloride.—The residue after estimation of the methoxyl group was warmed with a little acetic anhydride, diluted with ether and filtered. The solid was dissolved in 25% alcohol and to it was added a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid with a small speck of silver chloride in it. Hydrochloric acid (20%, 10 c.c.) was added to it and the alcohol was slowly evaporated on a water-bath. The solution was set aside for crystallisation. Needle-shaped violet crystals with a metallic lustre were obtained. It does not melt below 350°. It is highly soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohols giving purple-red solutions. Ferric chloride with alcoholic solution of the pigment gives a stable dark blue-green colour which changes to faint violet on dilution with water. On addition of warm water to alcoholic solution, the colour fades (leuco base) but soon a pale violet precipitate settles down. From the acid solution the pigment was completely taken up by amyl alcohol. Sodium carbonate produces a violet colour which turns blue on dilution. Lead acetate gives a violet precipitate. The amount of substance was too small for any further quantitative investigation. This work was done in the Technology laboratories of the Andhra University, Waltair.